

Impact Of Industry-Institution Partnership On Technical And Vocational Education And Training (TVET) Graduate Employability

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ABSTRACT

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) plays vital role in developing skilled workforce, equipping individuals with practical skills that is required for employment in various industries/workforce. However, TVET graduates are often faced with the challenge in securing employment due to mismatch between skills and industry requirements. The main objective of the study is thus; to assess the impact of industry-institution partnership and TVET graduates employability in Delta State, Nigeria, and the employment outcome. The study adopted a quantitative survey research that focused on graduates from polytechnics, monotechnics (specialized institution), and a specialized university, as well as representatives of these institutions using a stratified random sampling technique. Structured questionnaire serves as the primary data collection instrument. Variables were analyzed using statistical methods; the dependent variable is graduate employability, measured as a binary outcome (employed = 1, unemployed = 0). Independent variables include industry-related factors (internship participation, employer involvement in curriculum, industry collaboration type), and skill-related factors (technical skills, soft skills, digital skills). The study's logistic regression results emphasize the critical role of industry-institution partnership in enhancing graduate employability, as evidenced by a significant positive effect ($p = 0.021$, Exp (B) = 2.078). This indicates that graduates from institutions with strong industry collaborations are twice likely to secure employment compared to those without such linkages. Also, the study revealed large number of unemployed and self-employed graduates, this indicates that traditional employment opportunities are limited (inadequate regular job opportunities for TVET graduates). The study amongst others recommends that policymakers design and implement frameworks that formalize collaboration between TVET institutions and industries. These frameworks should include active employer participation in curriculum design, assessment, and job placement strategies.

Keywords: Industry-Institution Partnership, Graduates Employability, TVET, Entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

The pressing issue of unemployment among Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) graduates in Nigeria has sparked great concern and intense debate among stakeholders. Despite the country's growing population and increase demand for skilled workers, many TVET graduates are struggling to secure gainful employment. A potential solution to this challenge lies in fostering industry-institution partnerships. This collaborative or partnership approach brings together TVET institutions, industries, and government agencies to enhance graduates employability. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) plays a vital role in developing a skilled workforce, equipping individuals with practical skills that is required for employment in various industries in the world of work.

TVET institutions are expected to provide graduates with the necessary technical competencies to meet labor market demands. However, it is embedded with the traditional TVET model which often focus on theoretical instructions, neglecting practical's skills

and industry experience that are required by employers. Despite the growing emphasis on vocational education, many TVET graduates struggle to secure meaningful employment due to a mismatch between their skills and industry needs [1] This skills gap raises concerns about the effectiveness of Nigeria's TVET system and the extent of partnership between industry and training institutions

Industry-institution partnerships (IIP) are recognized globally as a key strategy for enhancing the employability of TVET graduates. IIP offer a promising solution to this challenge. By collaboration with industries, TVET institutions can adequately gain insight into the skills and competencies required by employers. This information can inform curriculum development, to ensure that TVET programs align with industry needs. Also, industry partners can provide students with practical training, internships and job opportunities in enhancing their employability. These partnerships ensure that training programs align with industry requirements, provide hands-on experience through internships and apprenticeships, and expose students to real-world of

work [2]. IPP stand as a panacea to bridging the gap by providing graduates with the practical skills needed and industry exposure needed in the world of work if effectively utilized. These partnerships are in various forms, which include apprenticeships, internships, collaborative research projects, industry-sponsored programs and mentorships programs [3]. However, in Nigeria, these partnerships have been a major concern to both institutions and industry this is because TVET graduates are often time confronted with the lack of practical industry exposure, with many training institutions operating with outdated curricula that do not reflect current technological advancements or workplace requirements. Without direct industry involvement, graduates often find themselves unprepared for the realities of the labor market, often time leading to high unemployment and underemployment rates among TVET graduates [4]. Strengthening industry-institution partnerships is therefore essential to bridging the gap and improving graduate employability.

Despite the importance in TVET education, TVET graduates are often faced with the challenge in securing employment due to inadequate exposure in skills development. In countries where such partnerships are well-developed, TVET graduates have higher employment rates and are better equipped to contribute to economic growth. However, in Nigeria, the current TVET system has a skill gap leading to unemployable graduates [5]. Although, there is rapid transformation in the Nigerian labor market due to technological advancements and evolving industry demands; sectors such as manufacturing, construction, and information technology require a workforce with specialized technical skills that TVET institutions can provide. However, without strong collaboration between industries and educational institutions, the skills gap will continue to widen. A structured partnership framework where industries contribute to curriculum development, provide mentorship opportunities, and participate in skill assessments, can significantly enhance TVET graduates' readiness for employment [6].

However, successful industry-institution partnerships have been observed in some countries, thereby providing valuable lessons for Nigeria. For example, Germany's dual vocational education system integrates classroom learning with practical industry training, ensuring that graduates possess both theoretical knowledge and hands-on experience. Similarly, China and Singapore have invested heavily in TVET-industry collaborations, leading to high employment rates among vocational graduates. Adopting similar models in Nigeria can improve the quality and relevance of TVET education, making graduates more competitive in the labor market.

Government policies can also play a crucial role in fostering industry-institution partnerships. In Nigeria, existing TVET policies emphasize skill acquisition but lack a clear implementation framework for sustained collaboration between educational institutions and industries. The significance of the study involves understanding how industry partnerships impact employability can help improve TVET programs effectiveness in preparing graduates for the job market through capacity building in entrepreneurship and findings can guide TVET institutions and industries in forming effective partnerships that boost graduate employability and the results might inform policy makers about the value of fostering industry TVET collaborations for better workforce outcomes through effective and efficient entrepreneurship

This study therefore, seeks to examine the current state of industry-institution partnerships in Nigeria's TVET institution and assessing the employment outcomes of TVET graduates with particular reference to Delta State. By analyzing the extent of industry involvement in training programs and the challenges faced by TVET graduates in securing employment, the study will provide insights into strategies for improving employability. Strengthening these partnerships is crucial for addressing the skills gap, reducing youth unemployment, and ensuring that TVET remains a viable pathway to economic development in Nigeria.

OBJECTIVES

The following are the research objectives

1. To investigate the impact of industry-institution partnership on TVET graduates' employability
2. To identify factors influencing TVET graduates employability
3. To examine employment outcomes and partnership experiences of TVET graduate

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Industry-Institution Partnership

This study therefore, seeks to examine the current state of industry-institution partnerships in Nigeria's TVET institution and assessing the employment outcomes of TVET graduates with particular reference to Delta State. By analyzing the extent of industry involvement in training programs and the challenges faced by TVET graduates in securing employment, the study will provide insights into strategies for improving employability. Strengthening these partnerships is crucial for addressing the skills gap, reducing youth unemployment, and ensuring that TVET remains a viable pathway to economic development in Nigeria.

Industry-institution partnerships have become increasingly important in enhancing employability

and addressing the skills gap in the labor market which are needed in the world of works. Industry-institution partnerships are collaborative relationships between industries and educational or research institutions whose aim is to drive innovation, sustainability, and economic growth. These partnerships are built on mutual benefit, where each partner brings unique assets, expertise, or market access in creating value.

According to [7] industry-institution partnership is a collaborative relationship between educational institutions and industry partners so as to provide students with practical skills and industry exposure needed for the job in the world of work. [8], argued that, industry-institution partnership is a collaborative relationship between TVET institutions and industry partners to provide students with practical skills, industry exposure, and employment opportunities. Similarly, [9] argues that, industry-institution partnership is a strategic alliance between educational institutions and industry partners to enhance employability and address the skills gap needed in the workforce. Industry-institution partnerships include; Internships apprenticeships, collaborative research projects, Industry-sponsored courses or programs and mentorship programs. If effectively utilized, the benefits are enormous, these includes; enhanced employability, practical skills development, industry exposure, networking opportunities and improved curriculum design. Studies have shown varying results of industry-institution partnerships. [10] argued how incentives offered by governments affect human capital accumulation, ultimately driving positive economic development externalities

TVET

TVET refers to “aspects of the educational process which involves, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupants in various sectors of economic and social life” [11a] and [11b]. TVET is dispensed in both public and private educational establishment and other forms of formal or informal instruction which is aimed at granting all segments of the society access to a life long learning resources.

In the 21st century, dominated by information and communication technology, and where labour market demands are changing constantly, providing relevant TVET programs to both boys and girls is deemed necessary to the effort to fostering sustainable development and eradicating extreme poverty and hunger in Africa and attaining rapid growth and subsequent development in Africa. [12] submitted that the goal of TVET is centered on producing both technical and semi-skilled manpower that is capable of reducing unemployment and restoring, and

sustaining economic growth and development. Similarly, [13] argued that technical and vocational education is geared towards solving current economic problems of a nation which result from high rate of unemployment, technological advancement, occupational mobility, and increase in the number of women in the workforce. TVET in Nigeria is aim in assisting the federal and state education authorities in their effort to revitalize reform and expand the provision of skills, vocations, science and technology so as to meet the nation’s present and future socio-economic needs [14] Industry institution partnerships improve access to vocational training opportunities and bridge the gap between TVET institutions and the implementation and management of industry-institution partnership to achieve good performance and improved TVET graduates’ employability [15a ;15b]. Similarly, [16] submitted that vocational and technical education students are perceived to have acquired entrepreneurial skills that impact their abilities and skills that could help equip them with the competencies needed for self-employment as graduates.

Employability

The concept of employability has gained significant attention in recent years, as the job market continues to evolve and the demand for skilled workers increases [17]. Employability refers to the ability of graduates to secure and maintain employment that are relevant to their skills, knowledge, and experience [18]. It involves a range of skills; technical skills, soft skills, and personal qualities. Employability encompasses the ability of the individuals to adapt to changing work environments and requirements [19]. Employability is not just about finding a job, but also about maintaining employment, adapting to the work ethics and the ability in advancing one’s career in relevant field. Various components of employability include technical skills, ICT, soft skills, personal qualities, and networking. Technical skills are specific, job-related skills that are typically acquired through formal education, training, or experience, that are mostly industry-specific and essential for performing specific tasks or jobs. While soft skills are non-technical skills that are essential for effective communication, teamwork, adaptability, networking, and leadership etc. Personal qualities, such as adaptability, resilience, and motivation, are critical for maintaining employment and advancing one’s career.

Also, networking is an important component of employability, as it enables graduates to build relationships with potential employers and advance their careers. Employability is a dynamic construct built around individual, encompassing career identity, management of self and professional development, social networks and environment monitoring [20]. Similarly, [21] submitted that employability is a

dynamic construct that includes individual competence, personal circumstances, and context.

Empirical Studies on Industry-Institution Partnerships

Some studies on industry-institution partnerships and TVET graduate employability: [22] examined employability of TVET Graduates through industry-institution partnership in Nigeria, using survey design, descriptive statistics and regression analysis; variables used are IIP, employability and TVET graduates. Their study revealed that IIP has a significant positive effect on TVET graduates employability. [23] examined the impact of industry-institution partnerships on the employability of TVET graduates. Using the survey research method and the online survey, ANOVA, regression analysis techniques.

The study found that graduates who participated in industry-institution partnerships had higher employability rates. [24] examined the impact of industry-institution partnership on graduates employability in Nigeria using the survey design, descriptive statistics and regression analysis, variables used are IIP, employability and TVET graduates. The result of their study revealed that IIP has significant positive impact on TVET graduates employability; practical skills training and mentorship were significant predictors for employment. [25] examined the Effects of Industry-Institution Partnerships on Students' Career Development, using the mixed-methods method and interviews, surveys, case studies technique.

The study found that students who participated in industry-institution partnerships had better career outcomes than those who did not. [26] investigated the implementation of work-integrated learning in Nigerian universities using the descriptive statistics survey research. Their study found that such programs were underutilized due to factors like poor teacher quality and lack of policy support. This shows the need to update the school curriculum to better meet the needs of the job market. [27] examined quality TVET internship: a veritable tool to bridge the gap between theory and practice. Their study highlights the importance of entrepreneurial skills, as self-employment was a major employment pathway for graduates

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This study adopted a quantitative survey research design to investigate the impact of industry-institution partnerships on TVET graduates' employability in Delta State, Nigeria. The research focused on graduates from polytechnics, monotchnics (specialized institution), and a specialized university, as well as institutional representatives involved in industry engagement,

curriculum development, and student placement initiatives. A structured questionnaire was used to collect data from TVET graduates and institutional representatives. The questionnaire consisted of several sections: Demographic information: Age, gender, institution, and field of study. Industry-institution partnership: Questions assessing the level of collaboration between TVET institutions and industries. .Employability: Questions measuring employment outcomes, job alignment, and skills acquisition and Internship experience: Questions evaluating the effectiveness of internships and industry participation in curriculum development. The study employed stratified random sampling techniques to select participants. A total of 120 questionnaires were distributed to TVET graduates through alumni networks, and 94 were successfully retrieved. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25. The following statistical techniques were used to achieve the various objectives:

Objective 1: Impact of Industry Institutions' Partnership on TVET Graduates' Employability

The dependent variable Employability was coded as a binary variable (employed = 1, unemployed = 0), while the independent variable; industry institution partnership was measured through survey questions assessing the level of collaboration between TVET institutions and industries. Logistic regression analysis was used to examine the relationship between industry-institution partnership and employment outcomes.

Objective 2: Factors Influencing TVET Graduates' Employability

Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and mean scores) were used to summarize trends in employment and industry collaboration. Logistic regression analysis was used to identify significant predictors of employability, including job alignment, internship participation, and industry participation in curriculum development.

Objective 3: Employment Outcomes and Partnership Experiences of TVET Graduates

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize employment outcomes, including employment rates and job alignment. Survey questions were used to gather data on TVET graduates' experiences with industry-institution partnerships, including internship effectiveness and industry participation in curriculum development.

This study aims to provide a clear and comprehensive understanding of the impact of industry-institution partnerships on TVET graduates' employability, by explicitly linking the methodology to each research objective

DATA PRESENTATION AND RESULT

Table 1: Employment Status of Graduates

	Count	Percent
Valid Employed (full-time)	7	7.5
Employed (part-time)	15	16.5
Self-employed	28	29.1
Still pursuing further education	27	28.4
Unemployed	17	18.4
Total	94	100.0

Table 1 presents the analysis of employment status of graduates in TVET institutions, with valid response; employed (full-time), part-time, self-employed, still pursuing further education and unemployed from respondents

The results indicate that only 7.5% of graduates are employed full-time, while 16.5% are working part-time. Significant proportions (29.1%) are self-employed, highlighting the role of entrepreneurship. Meanwhile, 28.4% are still pursuing further education, and 18.4% remain unemployed, reflecting potential challenges in labor market absorption.

Table 2: Job alignment with course of study

	Count	Percent
Valid No	67	70.9
Yes	27	29.1
Total	94	100.0

Table 2, presents an analysis of job alignment of graduates with their course of study, with Yes representing job alignment and No = Job disalignment

Majority (70.9%) of graduates reported that their jobs are not aligned with their course of study, while only 29.1% found jobs related to their field. This suggests a mismatch between education and labor market demands.

Table 3: Rating of relevance of skills in securing employment

Respondents	Mean	Mode
Technical Skills	3.9	4
Soft Skills	2.1	2
Digital/ ICT Skills	4.3	4
Entrepreneurial Skills	3.0	3
Problem Solving & critical thinking	3.0	2

Table 3: present respondents' rating of the relevance of skills in securing employment (1 = Not Important, 2 = Slightly Important, 3 = Moderately Important, 4 = Important, 5 = Very Important)

Digital/ICT skills (Mean = 4.3, Mode = 4) and technical skills (Mean = 3.9, Mode = 4) are rated the

most important for securing employment. Soft skills (Mean = 2.1) are perceived as the least important,

	Count	Percent
Valid No	51	54.4
Yes	43	45.6
Total	94	100

which could indicate a lack of awareness of their relevance

Table 4: Institution having structured partnership with industries

Table 4 presents institutions having structured partnership with industries, with Yes representing structured partnership with industries and No = not structured partnership with industries. From the result, only 45.6% of respondents confirmed that their institutions have structured partnerships with industries, while 54.4% reported no such partnerships.

	Count	Percent
Valid No	62	66.0
Yes	32	34.0
Total	94	100.0

This suggests a weak linkage between TVET institutions and the labor market.

Table 5: Internship Effectiveness

Table 5 presents institutions having internship effectiveness with industries, with Yes representing Valid for internship effectiveness with industries and No = representing non effectiveness with industries. From the result, majority (66.0%) of graduates felt that their internship experiences were not effective in enhancing employability, while only 34.0% found

	Count	Percent
Valid Moderately effective	26	27.66
Not Effective	35	37.23
Very Effective	33	35.1
Total	94	100.0

them beneficial. This implies a need for stronger industry engagement in internship programs.

Table 6: Partnership Effectiveness

Table 6 presents institutions having partnership effectiveness with industries, with Valid; moderately effective, not effective, and very effective with industries. From the result, 35% of respondents rated partnerships as very effective, a combined 65.0% found them either moderately effective (27.66%) not effective (37.23%), signaling gaps in collaboration efforts.

Table 7: Variables in the logistic regression Equation

	B	S. E	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp (B)
Step 1a Job Alignment	-689	.501	1.893	1	.169	.502
Internship participation	.740	.465	2.34	1	.011	.477
Internship Effectiveness	-.358	.499	.517	1	.472	.699
Industry Institution partnership	.731	.472	2.400	1	.021	2.078
Industry Participation & curriculum	.344	.468	-.538	1	.043	1.410
Technical Skills	-109	-178	.380	1	-.038	1.116
Soft Skills	-.082	.173	.225	1	.635	.921
Digital ICT Skills	0.36	.150	.050	1	.023	.065
Entrepreneurial Skills	.376	.170	4.882	1	.027	1.456
Problem Solving & Critical thinking	-.190	.172	1.231	1	.267	.827
Constant	-654	1.304	.251	1	.616	.520

Table 7 present Variables in the logistic regression equation emphasizing the critical role of industry-institution partnership in enhancing graduate employability.

The study's logistic regression results emphasize the critical role of industry-institution partnership in enhancing graduate employability, as evidenced by a significant positive effect ($p = 0.021$, $Exp(B) = 2.078$). This indicates that graduates from institutions with strong industry collaborations are more than twice as likely to secure employment compared to those without such linkages. Additionally, industry participation in curriculum development ($p = 0.043$, $Exp(B) = 1.410$) further improves employment prospects, suggesting that aligning TVET programs with industry needs enhances job relevance. However, internship participation ($p = 0.011$, $Exp(B) = 0.477$) was found to positively impact employability, indicating that current internship programs may be effective. This calls for a review of internship structures to ensure they provide meaningful hands-on experience. Moreover, entrepreneurial skills ($p = 0.027$, $Exp(B) = 1.456$) significantly contribute to employment opportunities, reinforcing the importance of equipping TVET graduates with self-employment training as an alternative to traditional job markets.

Table 8: Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	118.028a	.557	.615

Table 8 present the summary of the model result Estimation terminated at iteration number 4 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001. The Nagelkerke R Square value (0.615) suggests that the logistic regression model explains approximately 61.5% of the variance in employability outcomes, indicating a strong predictive capacity.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS AND IMPLICATIONS

The study gives important insight on the employability of TVET graduates in Delta State, Nigeria; how they can be gainfully employed, considering the role of partnerships between training institutions and industries. The large number of unemployed and self-employed graduates from the study indicates that traditional employment opportunities are limited (inadequate for TVET graduates); this is in consistence with [28] whose study revealed that, the current TVET system in Nigeria has a skill gap leading to unemployable graduates, The current trends implies the need for institutions to work more closely with industries to assist students get jobs after graduation Also, many graduates' finds themselves working in jobs that are not related to their field of study, this suggests a misalignment with what they were taught in school and what is needed by employers in the world of work; this is in consistence with [29] who their study found that programs taught in training institutions were underutilized due to factors; poor teacher quality and lack of policy support. This shows the need to update the school curriculum to better meet the needs of the job market and effective policy implementation

The study also highlights the critical role of industry-institution partnerships in improving employment outcomes. The logistic regression results confirm that such partnerships significantly increase the likelihood of graduate employment. This suggests that institutions with structured industry linkages provide better employment prospects for their graduates. However, the low percentage of respondents reporting effective industry partnerships indicates that these collaborations are either insufficient or ineffective in practice. Strengthening these partnerships through active industry participation in curriculum design, internships, and mentorship programs could help bridge the skills gap and improve graduate employability. Enhancing the quality of internship programs by ensuring that they

provide meaningful, hands-on experience would be crucial in improving employment outcomes; this is in consistence with [30] who advocated for quality TVET internships as a means to enhance hands-on experience and better prepare students for the workforce after graduation.

The study further highlights the importance of entrepreneurial skills, as self-employment was a major employment pathway for graduates. Given this, integrating more robust entrepreneurial training into TVET programs could equip graduates with the skills needed to create their own employment opportunities through entrepreneurship; this is in consistence with [31] who their study revealed that vocational and technical education students perceived themselves to have acquired entrepreneurial skills to a high extent, suggesting that integrating robust entrepreneurial training into TVET programs could equip graduates with the competencies needed for self-employment or in the world of work

The study also underscores the importance of digital and ICT skills in securing employment. For graduates who possessed strong digital skills were more likely to be employed, reflecting the increasing demand for tech-related competencies in the job market. This suggests that TVET institutions should prioritize digital literacy and technical skills training to enhance graduate competitiveness. The relatively low perceived importance of soft skills among respondents is a concern, as many employers value communication, teamwork, and adaptability. TVET programs should incorporate soft skills training alongside technical instruction to ensure graduates are well-rounded and prepared for diverse work environments.

The limitation of the study includes; findings which are specific to certain industries, locations and type of TVET programs, whereby selecting four institutions in Delta State Nigeria, thereby limiting generalizability. Data collection challenge, falsity of data; where respondents sometimes gives inaccurate information, and partnership variability; whereby different industry-institution partnerships might have different levels of engagement, and impacting results differently.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights a critical disconnect between the training received by TVET graduates and the actual demands of the labor market in Delta State, Nigeria. The findings have significant implications for each of the study's objectives.

Objective 1: Impact of Industry Institutions' Partnership on TVET Graduates' Employability. The study found a significant positive impact of industry-institution partnership on TVET graduate employability, supporting existing literature [32a ;

32b]. This finding aligns with the institutional governance and human capital theory which suggests that strong institutional governance can enhance employability; promoting relevant skills development and government initiatives can support education and training programs, increasing employability [33]. The study underscores the need for stronger partnerships between TVET institutions and industries to enhance employability; indicating that industry partnerships can play a crucial role in bridging the gap between TVET graduates' skills and employer expectations, enhancing employability. Objective Achieved

Objective 2: Factors Influencing TVET Graduates' Employability. The study identifies weak collaboration, ineffective internship experiences, and outdated curriculum as significant factors influencing TVET graduates' employability, aligning with previous research, [34a; 34b]. Objective Achieved

Objective 3: Employment Outcomes and Partnership Experiences of TVET Graduates

The study reveals a mismatch between TVET graduates' skills and employer expectations, highlighting the need for stronger industry-institution partnerships and industry participation in curriculum design and job placement strategies [35a; 35b]. Objective Achieved

The study recommends formalizing collaboration frameworks, restructuring internship programs, and continuously updating curricula to reflect labor market needs. Regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be implemented to assess the impact of these interventions on graduates' employment outcomes.

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